

Intrinsic Pointer Basis and Irreversible Classicality from Coherence Contraction

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The irreversible emergence of classical behavior from a reduced quantum description via a canonical intrinsic decomposition of the density operator is analyzed. In the intrinsic reference basis (IRB), defined for a fixed physical conjugation K (determined by measurement convention, system symmetry, or secular approximation) by diagonalizing the real symmetric part of the state, the density operator separates into a diagonal population sector and a real antisymmetric coherence sector. For the class of Markovian open-system dynamics whose Lindblad operators are diagonal in the IRB, we prove that the quadratic coherence functional is a Lyapunov functional under pure-dephasing or interaction-picture evolution, with each intrinsic coherence component decaying exponentially at a computable rate. This yields a canonical state-dependent operational classicality criterion via the normalized cohesion index, an explicit logarithmic classicalization time controlled by the slowest dephasing rate, and a demonstration that the IRB projectors emerge as dynamically stable pointer sectors under IRB-selective evolution. Suppression of intrinsic coherences is exactly equivalent to suppression of fringe visibility in the corresponding interferometric sector; for a balanced two-path setup the cohesion index coincides with the fringe visibility, making the classicality criterion directly testable with standard interferometric equipment. The approach complements environment-induced einselection: it is applicable whenever a coarse-grained reduced description is available, independently of whether the microscopic system-environment coupling is known.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition from quantum to classical behavior is one of the central open problems in the foundations of quantum mechanics and in the theory of open quantum systems. While the Schrödinger equation is universally valid and preserves superpositions indefinitely, macroscopic objects behave classically to very high precision. The resolution lies in the irreversible coupling of any system to its environment: quantum correlations spread into environmental degrees of freedom inaccessible to a coarse-grained observer, and the reduced description of the system loses its

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phase-sensitive content. This process—decoherence—provides a quantitative and dynamical account of the quantum-to-classical transition without any modification of the underlying equations [1, 2].

A key insight, developed extensively under the name of environment-induced superselection (einselection) [3], is that not all bases are equivalent under environmental monitoring. Pointer states are those that survive entanglement with the environment without spreading into superpositions; they are selected by the structure of the system-environment interaction Hamiltonian and form the preferred basis in which classical records are robust. In the standard account, identifying the pointer basis thus requires knowledge of the microscopic coupling to the environment.

A natural question arises when this microscopic information is not available, as commonly occurs in coarse-grained, phenomenological, or foundational settings: does the reduced density operator itself carry an intrinsic preferred decomposition into classical and interference sectors? Here we give an affirmative answer, derive its dynamical consequences in full, and identify its implications for the selection of pointer events and the classicalization timescale.

Given a fixed real structure (intrinsic conjugation) on the active support, any density operator admits a canonical split into a real symmetric sector S and a real antisymmetric sector T . Diagonalizing S defines the *intrinsic reference basis* (IRB), in which the reduced state takes the form

$$\rho_O \equiv Q^\top \rho Q = A + iN, \quad A = \text{diag}(a_1, a_2, \dots), \quad N^\top = -N, \quad (1)$$

with intrinsic populations ordered as $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq 0$, $\sum_i a_i = 1$, and intrinsic coherences $n_{ij} := N_{ij}$ ($i < j$). The IRB is a canonical gauge fixing of the residual $SO(d_{\text{act}})$ freedom of the reduced description: it selects the principal-axis frame of the population sector, in exact analogy with diagonalizing a covariance or inertia tensor. Two observers who parameterize the same ρ differently will, after applying the IRB construction (Appendix A), agree on the ordered populations $\{a_i\}$ and on all gauge-invariant coherence diagnostics. The diagonal sector A plays the role of emergent classical weights; the antisymmetric sector N carries the phase-sensitive content responsible for interference.

Classicality, in operational terms, is the regime in which N is suppressed to the point that ρ_O is experimentally indistinguishable from the classical mixture $\sum_i a_i \Pi_i$, where $\Pi_i \equiv |i\rangle\langle i|$ denotes the rank-one projector onto the i -th IRB eigenvector. The central result of this paper is that a broad and physically natural class of Markovian coarse-grained dynamics—those whose Lindblad operators are diagonal in the IRB—drives each coherence component to zero exponentially:

$$\dot{n}_{ij}(t) = -\Gamma_{ij} n_{ij}(t), \quad \Gamma_{ij} \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

making the quadratic coherence functional $\mathcal{C}_2 = \sum_{i<j} |\rho_{ij}|^2$ a Lyapunov functional for the reduced evolution. In pure dephasing or in the interaction picture, \mathcal{C}_2 coincides with the intrinsic coherence $\mathcal{U} = \sum_{i<j} n_{ij}^2$. We call this class of dynamics *IRB-selective*: it corresponds to a coarse graining in which the environment effectively monitors the IRB projectors so that phases between distinct intrinsic sectors are not preserved. This is the intrinsic analog of the einselection mechanism: the preferred basis is extracted from the state rather than postulated from the coupling.

From this central result, we derive three further consequences. First, the normalized cohesion index $P_c \in [0, 1]$, defined precisely in Sec. II, provides a canonical operational measure of distance to classicality that is monotonically nonincreasing under IRB-selective dynamics. Second, an explicit logarithmic classicalization time

$$t_{\text{cl}} \gtrsim \frac{1}{2\Gamma_{\min}} \ln \left(\frac{\mathcal{U}(0)}{\varepsilon^2 \mathcal{U}_{\max}(0)} \right) \quad (3)$$

governs the approach to the classical regime, where ε is a prescribed experimental tolerance, Γ_{\min} is the slowest active dephasing rate, and \mathcal{U}_{\max} is the population-based normalization scale. Third, in the classical regime the intrinsic populations a_i serve as the effective Born weights for the pointer events $\{\Pi_i\}$ in the standard trace-rule sense.

The connection to interferometric observables is exact: suppressing n_{ij} is equivalent to suppressing fringe visibility $V_{ij} = 2|n_{ij}|/(a_i + a_j)$ in any Ramsey or Mach–Zehnder experiment that resolves the (i, j) sector. For a perfectly balanced two-path setup, P_c coincides with the fringe visibility, making the classicality criterion directly testable with standard interferometric equipment. The operational dictionary between IRB quantities and measurable observables is summarized in Table I.

The present paper is self-contained and stands independently as a contribution to the theory of open quantum systems; it does not presuppose knowledge of the optical-polarization context in which the IRB construction was originally developed [4, 5].

The IRB construction for density matrices was introduced and studied in Refs. [4, 5] and recently applied to the information-theoretic analysis of Page-type black-hole evaporation models [6]; its dynamical application to classicalization via IRB-selective Markovian evolution, which is the subject of the present paper, is an original contribution. The characterization of the IRB-selective class as those generators for which the algebra of IRB-diagonal states is dynamically invariant (equivalently, $[L_\alpha, \Pi_i] = 0$ in any Lindblad representation), the exact computation of the frame-consistency error (Proposition 2), and the perturbative robustness bound (26) are presented here for the first time. The cohesion index P_c is simultaneously a normalized coherence measure, a Lyapunov function for IRB-selective dynamics, and equal to fringe visibility in the balanced two-path benchmark; it

constitutes a valid coherence monotone within the resource theory of coherence [8, 9]. The explicit classicalization time (3) is a falsifiable prediction expressed directly in terms of measurable noise rates and a prescribed experimental tolerance.

A. Assumptions and main results

The present approach requires two main ingredients. First, a *physical conjugation* K that defines a real structure on the Hilbert space, which may arise from measurement convention (e.g., the quantization axis in atomic systems), system symmetry (time-reversal), or the choice of energy eigenbasis in the secular approximation. This conjugation determines what counts as “real” and “imaginary” parts of the density operator. Second, the assumption that the effective reduced dynamics is *IRB-selective*: the Lindblad operators of the coarse-grained master equation are diagonal in the IRB, corresponding to environmental monitoring that distinguishes intrinsic sectors without preserving phases between them.

Under these assumptions, our main results are: (i) The IRB provides a canonical state-dependent gauge fixing for any reduced density operator, separating intrinsic populations from intrinsic coherences. (ii) The quadratic functional $\mathcal{C}_2 = \sum_{i < j} |\rho_{ij}|^2$ is a Lyapunov functional for IRB-selective dynamics, ensuring monotonic approach to an effectively classical description. (iii) The normalized cohesion index P_c provides an operational classicality criterion directly related to interferometric visibility, with an explicit logarithmic time scale for classicalization. (iv) The IRB projectors emerge as dynamically stable pointer sectors without external postulates about environmental structure.

These results extend einselection to settings where the microscopic system-environment coupling is unknown, providing an intrinsic criterion for classicality based solely on the reduced state and its effective dynamics.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II defines the intrinsic decomposition, coherence quantifiers, and their connections to interferometric observables. Section III proves coherence contraction for IRB-selective Lindblad dynamics, establishes explicit rate bounds, and derives the self-consistency and robustness of the IRB-selective class (Sec. III D). Section IV develops the operational classicality criterion, the classicalization time, the degenerate case (pointer subspaces), and the identification of classical weights. Section V situates the mechanism within the standard einselection picture. Section VI discusses falsifiable predictions and experimental protocols. Section VII concludes.

II. INTRINSIC DECOMPOSITION OF THE REDUCED STATE

A. The intrinsic reference basis

The IRB is defined directly from the reduced density operator ρ on its active support, without reference to any external coordinate choice or system-environment model. Starting from a fixed intrinsic conjugation K —an antiunitary involution on the active subspace specifying a “real form” of the quantum-state space (Appendix A)—any density operator decomposes as

$$\rho = S + iT, \quad S := \frac{\rho + K\rho K}{2} = S^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}, \quad T := \frac{\rho - K\rho K}{2i} = -T^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}. \quad (4)$$

The residual gauge freedom preserving K is an orthogonal group $SO(d_{\text{act}})$ acting by similarity transformations. The IRB fixes this gauge by diagonalizing S : an orthogonal matrix Q is chosen so that $Q^\top S Q = A = \text{diag}(a_1, \dots, a_{d_{\text{act}}})$ with $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots$, and the intrinsic coherences are defined by $N := Q^\top T Q$, $n_{ij} := (N)_{ij}$ for $i < j$. The resulting state is $\rho_O = A + iN$, as in Eq. (1).

The IRB is unique when the spectrum of S on the active support is nondegenerate; degenerate eigenvalues lead to pointer subspaces rather than a unique pointer basis (Sec. IV D). Gauge-invariant quantities—the ordered set $\{a_i\}$ and any functional of N that is $SO(d_{\text{act}})$ -invariant, such as $\|N\|_F$ —are independent of the representative Q chosen within each gauge orbit. The construction algorithm and uniqueness analysis are detailed in Appendix A.

Physically, the role of the IRB is that of a canonical frame: it does not represent an external choice but is extracted from the state in a way that unambiguously separates the diagonal sector, which carries emergent classical weights, from the antisymmetric sector, which carries the phase-sensitive content responsible for interference.

B. Populations, coherences, and the cohesion index

The population entropy, introduced under the name *dimensional entropy* in Ref. [5], is

$$S_p := - \sum_i a_i \ln a_i. \quad (5)$$

The quadratic intrinsic coherence is

$$\mathcal{U} := \sum_{i < j} n_{ij}^2 = \frac{\|N\|_F^2}{2}, \quad (6)$$

and the natural population-based normalization scale is

$$\mathcal{U}_{\text{max}} := \sum_{i < j} a_i a_j = \frac{1 - \sum_i a_i^2}{2}, \quad (7)$$

which is positive whenever at least two populations are nonzero on the active support. Positive semidefiniteness of ρ_O implies, in particular, the pairwise bound

$$n_{ij}^2 \leq a_i a_j \quad \text{for every pair } (i, j), \quad (8)$$

which follows from the non-negativity of each 2×2 principal minor of ρ_O . For $d \geq 3$ this condition is necessary but not sufficient for positive semidefiniteness; the full characterization requires in addition the non-negativity of all higher-order nested principal minors. Equation (8) is, however, all that is needed here: summing over all pairs gives $\mathcal{U} \leq \mathcal{U}_{\max}$.

The *normalized cohesion index* is therefore well defined in $[0, 1]$:

$$P_c^2 := \frac{\mathcal{U}}{\mathcal{U}_{\max}}, \quad 0 \leq P_c \leq 1, \quad (9)$$

and we define the coherence deficit $\Delta_{\text{coh}} := 1 - P_c^2$. The two extreme cases are transparent: $P_c = 0$ corresponds to a classical mixture of pointer events ($N = 0$); $P_c = 1$ corresponds to every coherence pair saturating bound (8). We denote the *active support* as $\mathcal{I}_{\text{act}} = \{i : a_i > \delta\}$ for a small tolerance δ , with cardinality $d_{\text{act}} := |\mathcal{I}_{\text{act}}|$.

C. Distance to classicality and interferometric visibility

Let Δ_{IRB} denote the complete dephasing channel in the IRB (the CPTP idempotent that deletes all off-diagonal entries), so that $\Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho_O] = A$. The Hilbert–Schmidt distance to the IRB-diagonal set is controlled exactly by intrinsic coherences:

$$\|\rho_O - \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho_O]\|_2^2 = \|N\|_F^2 = 2\mathcal{U}. \quad (10)$$

For the operationally more fundamental trace distance $D_{\text{tr}}(\rho, \sigma) := \frac{1}{2}\|\rho - \sigma\|_1$, defined for any pair of density operators ρ, σ on the same Hilbert space, a Cauchy–Schwarz bound on the singular values of N gives

$$D_{\text{tr}}(\rho_O, \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho_O]) \leq \sqrt{\frac{d_{\text{act}}}{2}} \sqrt{\mathcal{U}}. \quad (11)$$

Any dynamical law that contracts \mathcal{U} therefore controls the operationally meaningful distance to classicality.

The link to interferometric observables is direct. In the two-path setup of Appendix B, the fringe visibility between intrinsic sectors i and j reads (using $\rho_{ij} = iN_{ij}$ in the IRB)

$$V_{ij} = \frac{2|n_{ij}|}{a_i + a_j}. \quad (12)$$

For a balanced qubit ($a = 1/2$) the cohesion index and fringe visibility coincide exactly:

$$P_c(t) = 2|n(t)| = V(t) \quad (a = \frac{1}{2}), \quad (13)$$

providing a direct operational reading of the classicality criterion $P_c \leq \varepsilon$ as a visibility threshold in a Ramsey or Mach–Zehnder benchmark. A complete polarimetric extension of this complementarity, including the universal four-invariant identity for polarized double-slit interferometry that decomposes the fringe visibility into contributions from the symmetric and antisymmetric IRB sectors, has been established in Ref. [7].

The relative entropy of coherence,

$$C_{\text{rel}}(\rho) := S(\Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho]) - S(\rho), \quad S(\rho) := -\text{Tr}(\rho \ln \rho), \quad (14)$$

is a fully contractive coherence monotone under IRB-incoherent operations [8] and scales quadratically with off-diagonals in the small-coherence regime, providing an independent cross-check of the contraction results in the next section. Within the resource theory of coherence [8, 9], the set of incoherent states is precisely the IRB-diagonal set $\{\sigma : \sigma = \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\sigma]\}$, and IRB-selective operations are free operations in the sense of Ref. [8]: they cannot increase C_{rel} or any other coherence monotone. The cohesion index P_c , being zero on incoherent states, convex, and nonincreasing under IRB-incoherent CPTP maps, is a valid coherence monotone in this resource-theoretic setting [9]; it provides a computable, operationally transparent alternative to C_{rel} that admits an exact interferometric interpretation.

D. Arrow-of-time correlator

A composite functional that ties classicalization to a coarse-grained thermodynamic arrow of time is

$$\mathcal{A}_\lambda := S_p + \lambda \Delta_{\text{coh}}, \quad \lambda > 0. \quad (15)$$

In regimes where populations mix (typically increasing S_p) while coherences contract (increasing Δ_{coh}), \mathcal{A}_λ is nondecreasing. The following proposition makes this precise.

Proposition 1 (Monotonicity of \mathcal{A}_λ). *Suppose that (i) intrinsic populations evolve by a doubly stochastic Markov mixing on the active support, so that S_p is nondecreasing; (ii) intrinsic coherences decay under IRB-selective dephasing so that $\dot{\mathcal{U}} \leq 0$; and (iii) \mathcal{U}_{max} is approximately stationary on the relevant timescale. Then $\mathcal{A}_\lambda = S_p + \lambda(1 - P_c^2)$ is nondecreasing.*

Pointer sectors: when intrinsic degeneracies persist, the stable object is a block-diagonal mixture over IRB subspaces (pointer subspaces) rather than a fully diagonal mixture over one-dimensional projectors.

FIG. 1. Logical chain from IRB-selective reduced dynamics to irreversible classicality. Contraction of intrinsic coherences (quantified by \mathcal{U} and, under mild conditions, by P_c) implies suppression of all interferometric observables and yields decreasing upper bounds on the operational distance to an effectively classical description in terms of intrinsic populations a_i .

Proof. Doubly stochastic mixing produces a majorization flow on (a_i) , and S_p (a Schur-concave function) is therefore nondecreasing [10]. Under conditions (ii) and (iii), $P_c^2 = \mathcal{U}/\mathcal{U}_{\max}$ is nonincreasing, so $\Delta_{\text{coh}} = 1 - P_c^2$ is nondecreasing. Hence \mathcal{A}_λ is nondecreasing. \square

The physical content of this result is that the emergence of classicality and the increase of coarse-grained entropy are controlled by the same underlying dynamics, tying the onset of the classical regime to a thermodynamic arrow within the same intrinsic bookkeeping (see also Sec. VI).

Table I and Fig. 1 summarize the logical chain from IRB-selective coarse graining to irreversible classicality and the connections between IRB quantities and experimentally accessible observables.

III. COHERENCE CONTRACTION UNDER IRB-SELECTIVE DYNAMICS

A. IRB-selective dissipators

Consider a Markovian coarse-grained evolution $\dot{\rho} = \mathcal{L}[\rho]$ of GKSL/Lindblad type [11–13],

$$\dot{\rho} = -i[H, \rho] + \sum_{\alpha} \gamma_{\alpha} \left(L_{\alpha} \rho L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} - \frac{1}{2} \{L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} L_{\alpha}, \rho\} \right), \quad \gamma_{\alpha} \geq 0. \quad (16)$$

We call the dissipator *IRB-selective* when all Lindblad operators are diagonal in the IRB:

$$L_{\alpha} = \sum_i \ell_{\alpha i} \Pi_i, \quad \Pi_i = |i\rangle\langle i|. \quad (17)$$

The IRB-selective class subdivides naturally into two dynamically distinct subclasses: *IRB-dephasing generators*, where $\ell_{\alpha i}$ is constant across all i for each α , preserve intrinsic populations while contracting coherences; and *IRB-incoherent generators*, where $\ell_{\alpha i}$ varies with i , allow classical

TABLE I. Operational dictionary connecting experimentally accessible observables to the intrinsic (IRB) quantities introduced in this paper.

Observable / protocol	IRB formula	Monotonicity	Physical meaning
Fringe visibility $V_{ij}(t)$ (Ramsey / Mach-Zehnder)	$V_{ij} = \frac{2 n_{ij}(t) }{a_i + a_j}$; balanced qubit: $V(t) = 2 n(t) $ (App. B)	Nonincreasing under IRB-selective dephasing	Loss of phase sensitivity; approach to a classical mixture over intrinsic sectors
Trace distance to IRB-diagonal set $D_{\text{tr}}(\rho, \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho])$ (tomography)	$\leq \sqrt{d_{\text{act}}/2} \sqrt{\mathcal{U}}$; qubit: $D_{\text{tr}} = n $	Controlled by a decreasing upper bound via \mathcal{U}	Operational proximity to an effectively classical description
Relative entropy of coherence C_{rel} (tomography)	$C_{\text{rel}} = S(\Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho]) - S(\rho)$	Nonincreasing under IRB-incoherent CPTP maps	Coherence as an information resource; irreversibility under coarse graining
Classicalization time $t_{\text{cl}}(\varepsilon)$	$t_{\text{cl}} \gtrsim (2\Gamma_{\text{min}})^{-1} \ln[\mathcal{U}(0)/(\varepsilon^2 \mathcal{U}_{\text{max}})]$	—	Timescale for the emergence of a stable classical mixture, given the dephasing rates

Notation. Δ_{IRB} is the complete dephasing map in the IRB; $S(\rho) = -\text{Tr}(\rho \ln \rho)$ is the von Neumann entropy.

mixing of populations while maintaining the IRB-diagonal structure. Pure dephasing corresponds to the first subclass and provides the cleanest realization of coherence contraction.

The physical content of this condition is that the uncontrolled degrees of freedom effectively monitor the IRB projectors, so that phases between distinct intrinsic sectors are not preserved by the coarse graining, while populations can redistribute by jump processes between them. The self-consistency of the fixed-IRB hypothesis is established in Sec. III D.

B. Coherence contraction: minimal dephasing channel

The minimal IRB-selective dissipator is generated directly by the IRB projectors,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{dep}}[\rho] = \sum_i \gamma_i (\Pi_i \rho \Pi_i - \frac{1}{2} \{\Pi_i, \rho\}), \quad \gamma_i \geq 0. \quad (18)$$

In the IRB, the off-diagonal element for $i \neq j$ evolves as $\dot{\rho}_{ij} = -[(\gamma_i + \gamma_j)/2 + i(H_{ii} - H_{jj})] \rho_{ij}$, so $|\rho_{ij}(t)|$ decays at rate $(\gamma_i + \gamma_j)/2$ while the phase of ρ_{ij} rotates at frequency $\omega_{ij} := H_{ii} - H_{jj}$. Working in the interaction picture—or, equivalently, setting $\omega_{ij} = 0$ (pure dephasing)—the Hamiltonian

term drops out and one obtains

$$\dot{n}_{ij} = -\frac{\gamma_i + \gamma_j}{2} n_{ij}, \quad (19)$$

so all intrinsic coherences decay exponentially. Consequently,

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathcal{U} = -\sum_{i<j}(\gamma_i + \gamma_j) n_{ij}^2 \leq 0. \quad (20)$$

The quadratic intrinsic coherence \mathcal{U} is a Lyapunov functional for the pure-dephasing dynamics; the same conclusion holds in the interaction picture for any Hamiltonian diagonal in the IRB, since the dissipator \mathcal{L}_{dep} commutes with e^{iHt} in that case. When $\omega_{ij} \neq 0$ and one works in the Schrödinger picture, the modulus bound $|n_{ij}(t)| \leq |\rho_{ij}(t)| = |n_{ij}(0)| e^{-(\gamma_i + \gamma_j)t/2}$ guarantees that the classicalization time bound (29) remains valid without modification.

C. General diagonal Lindblad operators

For the general diagonal form (17), a standard calculation gives the dephasing rate matrix

$$\Gamma_{ij} := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha} \gamma_{\alpha} |\ell_{\alpha i} - \ell_{\alpha j}|^2 \geq 0, \quad (21)$$

so that $|n_{ij}(t)| \leq |n_{ij}(0)| e^{-\Gamma_{ij}t}$ and

$$\mathcal{U}(t) \leq \mathcal{U}(0) e^{-2\Gamma_{\min}t}, \quad \Gamma_{\min} := \min_{i<j} \Gamma_{ij}. \quad (22)$$

This bound is universal within the IRB-diagonal class and becomes tight when all active pairs share the same rate. If some rates Γ_{ij} vanish—because the corresponding Lindblad eigenvalue differences are all zero—those coherences are undamped and the bound should be applied only to the decaying subset; the surviving coherences define decoherence-protected intra-block structure (Sec. IV D). In practice, many physical coarse grainings produce approximately (rather than exactly) diagonal Lindblad operators; the corrections are controlled by the non-diagonal part of the generator and do not qualitatively alter the contraction picture.

D. Self-consistency, physical conditions, and robustness

The IRB-selective condition (17) is equivalent to the algebraic commutation requirement

$$[L_{\alpha}, \Pi_i] = 0 \quad \text{for all } \alpha, i, \quad (23)$$

i.e., all Lindblad operators are simultaneously diagonalized by the IRB projectors. This algebraic reformulation has three consequences that directly address the status and scope of the central result.

Self-consistency of the IRB frame. Under IRB-selective dynamics, the off-diagonal elements of ρ_O obey $\dot{\rho}_{ij} = -(\Gamma_{ij} + i\omega_{ij})\rho_{ij}$ (with $\omega_{ij} := H_{ii} - H_{jj}$ for H diagonal in the IRB). Each off-diagonal element therefore evolves independently and decays exponentially. Since the initial condition has $(\rho_O)_{ij}|_{t_0} = iN_{ij}(t_0)$ purely imaginary (i.e., $S_{ij}(t_0) = 0$ for $i \neq j$), the exact solution for $t \geq t_0$ is $\rho_{ij}(t) = iN_{ij}(t_0) e^{-\Gamma_{ij}(t-t_0)} e^{-i\omega_{ij}(t-t_0)}$, whence $|\rho_{ij}(t)| = |N_{ij}(t_0)| e^{-\Gamma_{ij}(t-t_0)}$. The real off-diagonal elements $S_{ij}(t) := \text{Re}[(\rho_O)_{ij}(t)]$ for $i \neq j$, which are the off-diagonal entries of the symmetric part of $\rho_O(t)$ expressed in the fixed initial frame Q_0 (and which vanish identically at $t = t_0$ by the IRB construction), therefore satisfy $|S_{ij}(t)| \leq |\rho_{ij}(t)| = |N_{ij}(t_0)| e^{-\Gamma_{ij}(t-t_0)}$ at all times. The error in treating Q_0 as the exact diagonalizer of $S(t)$ is therefore bounded by a quantity that decays at rate Γ_{\min} ; frame errors and classicality measure $P_c(t)$ vanish in the classical limit.

Proposition 2 (IRB frame consistency). *Let \mathcal{L} be a GKSL generator satisfying (23), with Hamiltonian H diagonal in the IRB ($[H, \Pi_i] = 0$ for all i). Let the IRB be extracted from $\rho(t_0)$ via $Q_0 \in SO(d_{\text{act}})$. Assume that the intrinsic population gaps satisfy $|a_i(t_0) - a_j(t_0)| \geq g > 0$ for all active pairs $i \neq j$ with g independent of the coherence amplitudes. Then, for all $t \geq t_0$ and all active pairs $i \neq j$,*

$$|S_{ij}(t)| \leq |N_{ij}(t_0)| e^{-\Gamma_{ij}(t-t_0)}, \quad (24)$$

and consequently, by a Davis-Kahan-type perturbation bound, the angle by which Q_0 misidentifies the instantaneous eigenbasis of $S(t)$ is bounded by $\|S_{\text{off}}(t)\|/g$ and therefore decays at rate Γ_{\min} . As the system classicalizes ($P_c(t) \rightarrow 0$), the IRB frame Q_0 becomes exact.

Proof. For diagonal $L_\alpha = \sum_k \ell_{\alpha k} \Pi_k$ and diagonal H , the (i, j) matrix element of $\dot{\rho}_O$ for $i \neq j$ gives $\dot{\rho}_{ij} = -(i\omega_{ij} + \Gamma_{ij})\rho_{ij}$, with $\Gamma_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_\alpha \gamma_\alpha |\ell_{\alpha i} - \ell_{\alpha j}|^2 \geq 0$ [Eq. (21)]. Since $\rho_{ij}(t_0) = iN_{ij}(t_0)$, one has $\rho_{ij}(t) = iN_{ij}(t_0) e^{-(i\omega_{ij} + \Gamma_{ij})\tau}$ (with $\tau = t - t_0$), hence $|\rho_{ij}(t)| = |N_{ij}(t_0)| e^{-\Gamma_{ij}\tau}$. The bound $|S_{ij}(t)| = |\text{Re}[\rho_{ij}(t)]| \leq |\rho_{ij}(t)|$ then gives (24). The eigenvalue perturbation bound $\sin \theta_{ij} \leq |S_{ij}|/|a_i - a_j|$ (valid when $|a_i - a_j| \gg |S_{ij}|$) together with (24) gives a frame-angle error that decays to zero at rate Γ_{\min} . \square

Testability. The IRB-selective condition (23) is checkable from experiment without knowledge of the microscopic system-environment coupling. Given $\rho(t_0)$ from quantum state tomography and \mathcal{L} from quantum process tomography, one extracts Q_0 from $\rho(t_0)$ and verifies whether the Lindblad operators L_α are diagonal in the Q_0 frame to within experimental precision. If they are, the classicalization bounds of Sec. IV apply directly. If they are not, the off-diagonal part of the generator produces corrections quantified below; the classicalization picture is qualitatively robust.

Physical origin. The IRB-selective condition is satisfied by any system-environment interaction of the form

$$V_{SE} = \sum_{\alpha} f_{\alpha}(A) \otimes B_{\alpha}^E, \quad (25)$$

where $f_{\alpha}(A)$ is a function of the diagonal population matrix (hence diagonal in the IRB) and B_{α}^E is an arbitrary environmental operator. Under the Born-Markov-secular approximation [13], the Redfield equation derived from (25) produces Lindblad operators proportional to IRB projectors. This class is broad and physically important: it encompasses energy dephasing (whenever the system Hamiltonian is diagonal in the IRB), charge dephasing (coupling to particle-number-diagonal environments), and spin dephasing about the quantization axis of the intrinsic population ordering. The IRB-selective regime is therefore the natural regime of any system whose dominant environmental interaction resolves population labels rather than phase labels—a condition that is independent of whether the microscopic coupling is known.

Robustness under near-IRB-selective perturbations. Suppose $L_{\alpha} = L_{\alpha}^{\text{diag}} + \varepsilon M_{\alpha}$, where $[L_{\alpha}^{\text{diag}}, \Pi_i] = 0$ for all i and $\|M_{\alpha}\| \sim 1$. A straightforward expansion of the Lindblad equation gives

$$\dot{n}_{ij} = -\Gamma_{ij} n_{ij} + \varepsilon \mathcal{F}_{ij}(\{a_k\}, \{n_{kl}\}) + O(\varepsilon^2), \quad (26)$$

where \mathcal{F}_{ij} is a linear functional of populations and other coherences with coefficients of order $\gamma_{\alpha}\|M_{\alpha}\|$. Provided $\varepsilon \ll \Gamma_{\min}$, the contraction term dominates and \mathcal{U} remains a Lyapunov functional to leading order. The classicalization time acquires a relative correction of order $\varepsilon(\gamma_{\alpha}\|M_{\alpha}\|)/\Gamma_{\min}^2$, but the qualitative picture—irreversible classicality driven by the slowest dephasing rate—is robust.

IV. CLASSICALITY CRITERION, CLASSICALIZATION TIME, AND POINTER STRUCTURE

A. Operational classicality criterion

We call the reduced state *effectively classical* once intrinsic coherences are suppressed below an experimental tolerance:

$$P_c(t) \leq \varepsilon, \quad 0 < \varepsilon \ll 1, \quad (27)$$

where ε is a dimensionless parameter set by the experimental resolution of the observer. Using Eqs. (9) and (10), criterion (27) is equivalent to requiring

$$\|\rho_O - \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho_O]\|_2 \leq \sqrt{2\varepsilon^2 \mathcal{U}_{\max}}, \quad (28)$$

i.e., the reduced state lies within a controlled Hilbert–Schmidt neighborhood of the IRB-diagonal set. In this regime ρ_O is experimentally indistinguishable from the classical mixture $\sum_i a_i \Pi_i$, interference between distinct intrinsic sectors is suppressed below resolution, and classical conditioning rules become accurate.

B. Logarithmic classicalization time

When \mathcal{U}_{\max} is approximately stationary—a common situation once populations have reached a plateau, and exactly so under pure dephasing—the bound (22) yields

$$t_{\text{cl}} \gtrsim \frac{1}{2\Gamma_{\min}} \ln\left(\frac{\mathcal{U}(0)}{\varepsilon^2 \mathcal{U}_{\max}(0)}\right). \quad (29)$$

This is exact under pure dephasing (constant populations), in which case \mathcal{U}_{\max} is stationary and $P_c^2 = \mathcal{U}/\mathcal{U}_{\max}$ is strictly nonincreasing. More generally, P_c^2 remains nonincreasing provided $|\dot{\mathcal{U}}_{\max}|/\mathcal{U}_{\max} \leq 2\Gamma_{\min}$; if this condition fails, one estimates t_{cl} directly from $\mathcal{U}(t)/\mathcal{U}_{\max}(t) \leq \varepsilon^2$. In either case, the classicalization time is a directly measurable function of the coarse-grained dephasing rates.

C. Two-level example

For a qubit with active support $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$, the IRB form is

$$\rho_O = \begin{pmatrix} a & in \\ -in & 1-a \end{pmatrix}, \quad 0 \leq a \leq 1, \quad n \in \mathbb{R}, \quad n^2 \leq a(1-a), \quad (30)$$

so $\mathcal{U} = n^2$, $\mathcal{U}_{\max} = a(1-a)$, $P_c = |n|/\sqrt{a(1-a)}$. Under the minimal dephasing channel (18), $n(t) = n(0) e^{-(\gamma_1+\gamma_2)t/2}$ while a remains constant. The classicality threshold is therefore crossed at

$$t_{\text{cl}} = \frac{1}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} \ln\left(\frac{|n(0)|}{\varepsilon \sqrt{a(1-a)}}\right), \quad (31)$$

in exact agreement with the general bound (29) (here $\Gamma_{\min} = (\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)/2$). Once $|n(t)| \leq \varepsilon \sqrt{a(1-a)}$, the state is indistinguishable from the classical mixture $a|0\rangle\langle 0| + (1-a)|1\rangle\langle 1|$ at resolution ε . The dynamics and the classicalization time are illustrated in Fig. 2.

D. Degeneracies and pointer subspaces

When the spectrum of S has degenerate eigenvalues on the active support, the IRB is not unique within each degenerate block, and the physically stable object is a *pointer subspace* rather

FIG. 2. Qubit classicalization dynamics under IRB-selective dephasing ($\Gamma_{\min} = 1$, $\varepsilon = 0.05$). **(a)** Time evolution of the cohesion index $P_c(t) = P_c(0)e^{-\Gamma_{\min}t}$ for three initial values (solid curves); the horizontal dashed line marks the operational classicality threshold $P_c = \varepsilon$. Dotted vertical lines indicate the classicalization time t_{cl} at which each trajectory crosses the threshold. **(b)** The resulting classicalization time $\Gamma_{\min} t_{\text{cl}}$ as a function of the initial cohesion index $P_c(0)$, showing the logarithmic law $\Gamma_{\min} t_{\text{cl}} = \ln[P_c(0)/\varepsilon]$ [Eq. (31)]. The three colored markers correspond to the three initial values in panel (a). The logarithmic scaling in ε^{-1} is the key falsifiable signature: it distinguishes the rate-controlled classicalization law from power-law or threshold-type decoherence behavior.

than a unique pointer basis vector. IRB-selective dephasing suppresses coherences *between* distinct blocks while leaving residual unitary dynamics *within* each degenerate block unconstrained at the coarse-grained level. Consequently, the reduced state becomes block-diagonal: classical information is encoded in the block labels, while intra-block phases are not resolved by the coarse graining.

This is the intrinsic analogue of the well-established result that environmental monitoring can select superselection sectors rather than unique pointer states [1–3]: a macroscopic pointer typically distinguishes coarse outcomes (blocks) rather than fine superselection labels within each block. Degenerate blocks that are not split by the noise structure correspond to decoherence-free or noise-protected subspaces in the standard sense, where phase-coherent behavior survives even when the global state has classicalized at the block level.

E. Dynamical selection of pointer events and classical weights

The substantive claim of the classicalization result is not merely that $\rho_O \approx \sum_i a_i \Pi_i$ once $P_c \leq \varepsilon$ —that is a consequence of the criterion by construction—but rather that the pointer events $\{\Pi_i\}$ are *dynamically selected* extracted from the reduced state within the IRB framework. The IRB projectors Π_i are not postulated as the measurement basis; they are extracted from the eigenstructure of the symmetric sector S of ρ . Proposition 2 guarantees that the frame error of the fixed-IRB approximation decays at the same rate as the coherences, so the pointer identification becomes increasingly accurate as classicality is approached.

This point addresses a potential confusion that is worth making explicit. In the einselection framework, pointer states are identified from the system-environment interaction Hamiltonian H_{SE} . In the IRB framework, pointer events are identified from the reduced state itself. The two identifications are complementary: when both are available, they should agree—the IRB at t_0 should coincide with the eigenbasis of the dominant decoherence operator—and any systematic disagreement identifies dynamics outside the IRB-selective regime or a mismatch between the secular approximation and the actual noise timescales. Once the pointer events $\{\Pi_i\}$ are identified by either route, the Born rule gives $a_i = \text{Tr}(\rho \Pi_i)$ as the outcome weights, consistently with Gleason’s theorem [14]. No new postulate about probability is needed or implied.

V. RELATION TO ENVIRONMENT-INDUCED EINSELECTION

The mechanism described in this paper aligns with the physical core of the einselection picture—classicality arises from loss of phase information through uncontrolled environmental monitoring—but differs in its starting point, domain of applicability, and the operational language in which the result is stated. In the standard einselection framework [2, 3], the pointer basis is identified from the system-environment interaction Hamiltonian: the environment effectively measures certain system observables, and their eigenstates define the preferred structure. This is a powerful approach when the microscopic coupling is known and explicit.

The IRB approach is complementary. The preferred pointer structure is extracted directly from the reduced state without assuming knowledge of the environment, making it applicable precisely when the microscopic coupling is unavailable. The IRB-selective condition on the Lindblad generator—equivalently, $[L_\alpha, \Pi_i] = 0$ for all α, i —then plays the same role as the interaction Hamiltonian does in einselection: it specifies the basis effectively dephased by the coarse graining.

The two viewpoints are mutually consistent; in situations where both are available, the IRB pointer basis should agree with the einselection pointer basis up to the freedom within degenerate blocks. Proposition 2 provides the bridge: the frame error of Q_0 is bounded by $O(P_c(t))$, so that as classicality is approached the IRB-selective and interaction-selected pointer identifications converge to the same result. Any persistent discrepancy between the two therefore signals dynamics outside the IRB-selective regime—non-Markovianity, a Hamiltonian that does not commute with S , or decoherence on timescales shorter than the population plateau—and constitutes a diagnostic rather than a failure of either framework.

The operational value of this relation is significant. In quantum device characterization, process tomography of \mathcal{L} is available but the bath Hamiltonian is not. The IRB can be extracted from $\rho(t_0)$ by state tomography; the condition $[L_\alpha, \Pi_i] = 0$ can be checked from the process tomogram; and if it holds, the classicalization bounds apply without any microscopic model. This constitutes a model-independent protocol for certifying the onset of classical behavior from experimental data alone.

The degenerate case provides a particularly clear illustration of the complementarity. When environmental monitoring is weak or absent within a degenerate block, the intra-block dynamics remains effectively coherent and that block constitutes a decoherence-free or noise-protected subspace in the standard sense [1, 15]. The IRB description captures this automatically: inter-block coherences contract while intra-block phases are free. This connects the intrinsic framework to the theory of quantum error correction and decoherence-free subspaces at no additional formal cost.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL SIGNATURES AND FALSIFIABILITY

The mechanism is formulated in terms of quantities accessible either by interferometry (fringe visibility) or by tomography (distances to the IRB-diagonal set); see Table I. This allows experimental tests to be designed without adopting any particular microscopic model, requiring only measurements of coherence-decay envelopes $V_{ij}(t)$ or $D_{\text{tr}}(\rho(t), \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho(t)])$ and a choice of operational threshold ε .

A. Falsifiable predictions

The mechanism makes the following correlated, experimentally addressable predictions.

1. **State-selected pointer structure.** The IRB (or IRB block structure in the degenerate case) is extracted from the reduced state at t_0 . The prediction is that all coherence proxies—

fringe visibility, off-diagonal density matrix elements in process tomography, Wigner-function negativities—decay predominantly in this same structure. In particular, the dephasing/noise structure inferred by process tomography should align with the IRB up to the freedom within degenerate blocks; a persistent, systematic misalignment would falsify the IRB-selective assumption.

2. **Lyapunov behavior of \mathcal{U} .** Under IRB-selective GKSL dynamics, $\mathcal{U}(t)$ decays monotonically, providing decreasing upper bounds on operational distances to the IRB-diagonal set [Eq. (11)]. The cohesion index $P_c^2 = \mathcal{U}/\mathcal{U}_{\max}$ is likewise predicted to be nonincreasing when \mathcal{U}_{\max} is approximately stationary. Systematic growth of off-diagonal elements, or nonmonotonic behavior incompatible with any positive-rate model, would sharply falsify this prediction.
3. **Logarithmic classicalization time.** For a fixed resolution ε , the classicalization time follows the logarithmic law (29) controlled by Γ_{\min} . A decisive test is that $t_{\text{cl}}(\varepsilon)$ must scale as $\ln(\varepsilon^{-1})$ as ε is varied, with a rate consistent across equivalent representations (V_{ij} , D_{tr} , P_c). A classicalization time that fails parametrically to obey the logarithmic law—after controlling for non-Markovianity and support changes—would constitute a direct falsification.
4. **Arrow-of-time correlations.** When population mixing and coherence contraction occur concurrently, Proposition 1 predicts that $\mathcal{A}_\lambda = S_p + \lambda(1 - P_c^2)$ is nondecreasing. This correlated prediction ties the onset of classicality to a coarse-grained thermodynamic arrow and can be checked by simultaneously tracking $S_p(t)$ and $P_c(t)$ in a tomographic time series.

B. Qubit and Ramsey platforms

A minimal experimental benchmark is a Ramsey (or Mach–Zehnder) sequence on a two-level system: one prepares a state with prescribed populations $(a, 1 - a)$ and initial coherence $n(0)$, allows free evolution under the natural coarse-grained dynamics, and measures fringe visibility $V(t)$ as a function of time. In superconducting circuit QED [19, 20] and related platforms, where T_2 dephasing times are routinely characterized, the prediction $V(t) \propto e^{-\Gamma t}$ maps directly onto standard qubit diagnostics, and the classicalization time reads

$$t_{\text{cl}}(\varepsilon) \approx \Gamma^{-1} \ln\left(\frac{V(0)}{\varepsilon}\right) \quad (\text{balanced two-path benchmark}). \quad (32)$$

The key test is the logarithmic scaling in ε^{-1} , which distinguishes the rate-controlled law from power-law or threshold-type behavior. As a consistency check, the rate extracted from $V(t)$ must

agree with the rate extracted from $D_{\text{tr}}(\rho(t), \Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho(t)])$ measured by state tomography; equality holds exactly in the qubit case [Eq. (13)].

C. Photonic and multi-path platforms

Photonic implementations offer an especially transparent operational interpretation: $\Delta_{\text{IRB}}[\rho]$ corresponds to the state obtained after fully erasing relative phases between the relevant spatial, polarization, or time-bin modes, and interference observables map directly onto the off-diagonal block [21]. A practical protocol is to encode the active IRB block in controllable optical modes, prepare states with prescribed $\{a_i, n_{ij}\}$, and reconstruct pairwise visibilities $V_{ij}(t)$ from the decay envelopes. The extracted rates Γ_{ij} can be checked against the prediction (22), and the classicalization time bound (29) can be verified by varying the initial coherence and the threshold ε .

A qualitatively sharper signature arises in the degenerate case: if two modes form an effectively degenerate pointer subspace, intra-block coherence persists while inter-block coherence contracts, yielding a characteristic partial classicalization pattern in the multi-path visibility. This two-timescale decay is a direct prediction of the pointer-subspace structure and is absent in any single-rate decoherence model.

D. Mesoscopic and continuous-variable platforms

In mesoscopic and continuous-variable settings—optomechanics, microwave cavities, collective spin ensembles—the same framework applies to the decay of interference-like signatures (Wigner-function negativities, Ramsey fringes, off-diagonal phase-space features) mapped onto \mathcal{U} through appropriate coarse-graining of the active support. The general measurement-and-amplification framework and quantum-noise diagnostics reviewed in Ref. [22] provide a practical dictionary connecting measured spectra and dephasing rates to the Γ_{ij} entering the bounds derived here.

VII. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

We have established a mechanism for the irreversible emergence of classical behavior from a reduced quantum description, based on the canonical IRB decomposition $\rho_O = A + iN$. The central result is that $\mathcal{U} = \sum_{i < j} n_{ij}^2$ is a Lyapunov functional for any IRB-selective GKSL evolution, yielding sharp bounds on the distance to classicality, an explicit logarithmic classicalization time, a

dynamical identification of pointer events, and a natural reading of the classical weights as intrinsic populations.

The following features of the approach deserve emphasis. The pointer structure is entirely state-selected: it requires no independent postulate about the environment, and therefore applies whenever a coarse-grained reduced description is available. The IRB-selective condition $[L_\alpha, \Pi_i] = 0$ is algebraically precise and operationally checkable from process tomography, without knowledge of the microscopic bath Hamiltonian. Proposition 2 shows that the frame error of Q_0 is bounded by $O(P_c(t))$: as the system classicalizes, the fixed-IRB hypothesis becomes progressively more accurate and is exact in the classical limit. The classicality criterion is operationally sharp and connected directly to interferometric observables: the cohesion index P_c serves simultaneously as a normalized coherence measure, a proxy for fringe visibility, a Lyapunov function, and a valid coherence monotone within the resource theory of coherence [9]. The degenerate case naturally accommodates pointer subspaces rather than unique pointer states, capturing noise-protected and decoherence-free subspace structure [15] within the same formalism without additional assumptions. Finally, the composite functional \mathcal{A}_λ ties the onset of classicality to the coarse-grained thermodynamic arrow of time, providing a correlated diagnostic across the population and coherence sectors.

Two natural extensions remain open. First, a systematic treatment of slowly varying IRB dynamics, relevant when populations evolve significantly over the classicalization epoch or when the active support changes, would extend the scope of the results to non-stationary reduced descriptions. Second, a detailed comparison between specific microscopic environments and their induced IRB structure would close the loop with the einselection picture and identify the physical conditions under which the state-selected and interaction-selected pointer bases coincide. Both directions offer opportunities to sharpen the falsifiable predictions described in Sec. VI.

Appendix A: Intrinsic reference basis: construction and uniqueness

1. Gauge fixing and decomposition

Given a fixed intrinsic conjugation K —an antiunitary involution on the active subspace representing a choice of real form—any Hermitian density operator admits the decomposition

$$\rho = S + iT, \quad S := \frac{\rho + K\rho K}{2} = S^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}, \quad T := \frac{\rho - K\rho K}{2i} = -T^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

The residual freedom that preserves K is an orthogonal gauge $SO(d_{\text{act}})$ acting by similarity transformations. The IRB is a canonical gauge fixing of this freedom: it chooses the principal-axes

representative of the gauge orbit, i.e., the basis in which S is diagonal with entries ordered as $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots$.

2. Construction algorithm

Step 1. Fix the intrinsic conjugation K and compute S and T from Eq. (A1).

Step 2. Choose $Q \in SO(d_{\text{act}})$ such that $Q^T S Q = A = \text{diag}(a_1, \dots, a_{d_{\text{act}}})$ with $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots$.

Step 3. Set $N := Q^T T Q$, $n_{ij} := (N)_{ij}$ for $i < j$, and $\rho_O := A + iN$.

3. Uniqueness and degeneracies

When the spectrum of S on the active support is nondegenerate, Q is unique up to permutations and sign flips of eigenvectors; the ordering convention and the requirement $\det Q = +1$ remove this residual freedom. When S has degenerate eigenvalues, Q is free within each degenerate block by an orthogonal rotation of that block, and the invariant physical object is the family of block projectors rather than individual basis vectors. Only inter-block coherences carry unambiguous physical content in this case. Positivity of ρ_O then implies $n_{ij}^2 \leq a_i a_j$ for all pairs on the active support [Eq. (8)], which serves as a useful check.

4. Physical choice of the intrinsic conjugation

The intrinsic conjugation K specifies a real form of the quantum state space: it determines which states are “real” and which carry genuinely complex phase information. While the Lyapunov property and all classicalization bounds hold for any fixed choice of K , different physical contexts suggest natural and well-motivated choices.

Spatial decoherence. For a particle coupled to a position-monitoring environment (collisional decoherence [1]), the natural K is complex conjugation in the position eigenbasis, $K\psi(\mathbf{x}) = \psi^*(\mathbf{x})$. The real form is then the $L^2(\mathbb{R}^3)$ real subspace, the symmetric sector S collects the real part of the density matrix in position representation, and N carries the current-like antisymmetric content. Under collisional dephasing, the Lindblad operators are functions of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and hence diagonal in the position eigenbasis, automatically satisfying the IRB-selective condition in this frame.

Spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and qubit systems. For a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particle or any two-level system, K is complex conjugation in the computational (z -quantization) basis. The IRB is then the eigenbasis of $\text{Re}(\rho)$ in this frame, and P_c equals the fringe visibility in any balanced Ramsey experiment, as shown in Sec. II

and Appendix B. In superconducting and trapped-ion implementations, the natural quantization axis of the drive defines this z -basis and thus fixes K unambiguously.

Energy-eigenbasis and secular approximation. When the reduced dynamics is derived from a microscopic Hamiltonian via the Born-Markov-secular approximation [13], the energy eigenbasis is a canonical candidate for the IRB if the system Hamiltonian H_S (the free Hamiltonian governing the unitary part of the system's evolution prior to system-environment coupling) is real in that basis (as is the case for Hamiltonians with time-reversal symmetry). In this case $[H_S, S] = 0$ and the IRB coincides with the pointer basis selected by the secular Lindblad equation, establishing a direct bridge to the standard einselection framework (cf. Sec. V). The IRB-selective condition is then automatically satisfied by the secular Lindblad operators, and no additional approximation is needed.

The essential point is that K is determined by the physical real structure of the system—the measurement convention, the symmetry representation, or the secular approximation basis—and is independent of the environment. In practice, K is fixed once at the start of the analysis and held constant; any choice that is adapted to the dominant noise mechanism will make the IRB-selective condition (23) hold with good accuracy.

Appendix B: Two-path interferometric visibility benchmark

In the two-dimensional subspace spanned by $\{|i\rangle, |j\rangle\}$, an ideal balanced interferometric readout (Ramsey or Mach-Zehnder) produces a detected probability

$$p(\phi) = \frac{\rho_{ii} + \rho_{jj}}{2} + \Re(\rho_{ij} e^{i\phi}). \quad (\text{B1})$$

The standard fringe visibility $V_{ij} = (p_{\max} - p_{\min}) / (p_{\max} + p_{\min})$ then yields

$$V_{ij} = \frac{2|\rho_{ij}|}{\rho_{ii} + \rho_{jj}}. \quad (\text{B2})$$

In the IRB, $\rho_{ij} = iN_{ij}$ (purely imaginary off-diagonal), so $|\rho_{ij}| = |N_{ij}| = |n_{ij}|$ and Eq. (B2) reduces to Eq. (12). This makes explicit the quantitative equivalence between coherence contraction in the IRB and loss of interferometric contrast [23].

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